

Constant Energy, Lack of Information Equilibrium and Time Reversal

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The notion of constant energy appears in classical mechanics (e.g. a particle moves such that the sum of its kinetic and potential energies is a constant), in classical statistical mechanics where the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability $\exp(-(.5mv^2 + V(x))/T)$ means different $v, V(x)$ pairs such that $.5mv^2 + V(x) = E$ have the same probability and in bound state quantum mechanics $\exp(-iEn t)$. Classical mechanics, classical statistical and quantum mechanics are considered to be three completely different theories, but we argue that a constant E with time reversal invariance is equivalent to a lack of information and equilibrium for all three. Thus there is perhaps an underlying idea pertaining to equilibrium scenarios in different physical theories.

Classical Mechanics, Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Bound States

Classical mechanics, statistical mechanics and quantum bound states seem to represent three very different theories yet the notion of constant energy seems to appear in all three. In classical mechanics one may have a particle in a conservative force field move such that total energy = kinetic energy + potential energy is a constant. One may argue that the particle evolves because it moves from x_1 at t_1 to x_2 at t_2 even though E (energy) is the same at all x and t . Given only E , however, one has no information of the x, t pair. The particle may be moving to the right or to the left. Thus there is a lack of information. We argue that this is due to time reversal invariance which holds for a conservative force field.

A classical statistical mechanical particle has a probability proportional to $\exp(- (.5mv^2 + V(x))/T)$. Like the classical mechanical particle given an E there is a lack of information because any v, x pair which yields a specific E for a "particle" has the same probability. The particle could be moving to the right or the left and the probability would be the same so there is time reversal invariance. Furthermore in classical statistical mechanics one may derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by considering two body interactions such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Taking \ln of the latter and equating with the former with a proportionality constant added yields $f(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. One may note that a collision $e_1 + e_2$ may become $e_3 + e_4$ or vice versa so there is time reversal symmetry.

For a quantum bound state E is constant even though there is a density profile in space there is still an equilibrium scenario we argue. Consider a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. We have argued in previous notes that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent two probability-like profiles which are shifted so as to indicate the direction in which the particle moves. For example $\exp(ipx)$ means motion to the right for positive p and $\exp(-ipx)$ to the left. Both of these have the same real part $\cos(px)$. In a bound state with $V(x) = V(-x)$ only $\cos(px)$ terms survive i.e. $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \cos(px)$. Thus one has lost all sense of direction i.e. there is time reversal symmetry.

Thus time reversal symmetry together with constant E seems to yield a lack of information which in turn is linked to the notion of equilibrium in all three cases. In other words equilibrium

seems to be characterized by constant E and time reversal symmetry leading to a lack of information perhaps regardless of the specific physical theory.

Lack of Time Reversal Symmetry

Having a constant E at each x, t point in a classical system does not imply a lack of information or equilibrium if one does not have time reversal symmetry. For a classical particle in a conservative force field if one is given E one does not know which v, x pair to choose. One might argue that a classical particle moving from x_1 to x_2 is evolving, but due to time reversal symmetry it could just as well be moving from x_2 to x_1 . In the case of a classical object with kinetic energy moving on a surface with friction there is a constraint (namely friction) which is not time reversal invariant. If a particle moves to the left it loses energy, if it moves to the right it loses energy. Potential energy on the other hand is time reversal invariant. If a particle moves to the right it may lose potential energy and gain kinetic, but then moving from right to left it gains potential energy and loses kinetic, so one may assign a constant energy which implies a lack of information and time reversal and thus a sense of equilibrium. For the case of friction, energy is also conserved overall, but there is no sense of time reversal symmetry so there is not a lack of information. Even though the same energy exists at x_1 and x_2 the friction constraint ensures that running a movie backwards and sending the particle backwards are different and so this is not an equilibrium problem.

Quantum Bound State

We wish to examine the quantum bound state in more detail. A free quantum particle has a wavefunction of $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$. We suggest keeping t and x independent, but note that the time and spatial parts have the same structure, but different frequencies/wavelengths. Thus there is a kind of symmetry between t and x . For a bound state problem a potential $V(x)$ which does not depend on t is often used. If one considers an ensemble of free particles one might ask: Why shouldn't one include $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ together with $\exp(ipx)$ for each p ? The objective is to find a solution that does not evolve in time so one expects a regular $\exp(-i E_n t)$ pattern for the solution where E_n is the bound energy. As noted above $\exp(ipx)$ represents motion in a certain direction in space, but superposition $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ yields $\cos(px)$ which loses all sense of forward or backwards motion i.e. the sense of time. Thus just like a classical problem, one may consider average kinetic energy and $V(x)$ without any sense of time in the problem i.e. a conservation of energy problem. This formalism assumes time reversal symmetry. Thus removing time and solving a differential equation (time-independent Schrodinger equation) in space seems to be equivalent to an equilibrium treatment of the problem.

Quantum Bound Density and Time Reversal Symmetry?

$\exp(ipx)$ which represents a free quantum particle leads to $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ i.e. which seems to describe the idea of uniform motion i.e. a kind of center of mass motion which moves smoothly through x . Even though there are probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and the shifted $\sin(px)$ the so-called center of mass motion is still uniform. In order to create $\exp(ipx)$ one must break time reversal symmetry i.e. include two pieces $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ such that p and $-p$ yield different solutions so they are distinguishable as wavefunctions i.e. one can distinguish motion to the right and to the left. Both motions, however, are uniform - it does not matter in which direction the particle moves if one is only interested in $P(x)$ i.e. the classical probability to find the particle at x . This result has to be invariant with respect to time reversal.

Thus one has a probability type function $\exp(ipx)$ describing a free quantum particle. This function is not time reversal invariant i.e. $p \rightarrow -p$ does not yield the same result. Superposition, however, may make it time reversal invariant i.e. $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \rightarrow \cos(px)$. This result, however, still depends on p and so may be used in a statistical problem to create an average kinetic energy. $\cos(px)$, however, does not describe the uniform "center of mass" type motion of a free particle, however, and so cannot represent $P(x)$, the classical probability of a free particle. Interestingly, one may bring in time reversal invariance in two ways, using an OR probability approach i.e. adding $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ or using an AND approach and multiplying. The OR approach seems to apply to a physical equilibrium scenario in which one may have an $\exp(ipx)$ or an $\exp(-ipx)$ interacting, yet the overall result must be time reversal invariant to represent an equilibrium. Suggesting that an AND situation (as in (1)) should erase any information about peaks and troughs and only yield information about uniform center-of-mass motion then yields $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$.

In fact, it seems that one may use these arguments to define $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. assume a probability like form $f(px)$ from the classical action $-Et+px$ as describing a free particle. Then:

$$f(px) + f(-px) = \text{even function in } p \quad ((1a))$$

$$f(px) f(-px) = \text{constant to describe } P(x) \text{ i.e. the uniform center of mass motion.} \quad ((1b))$$

((1b)) suggests that $f(px) = a^{px}$ while ((1a)) suggests that $f(px)$ should be $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus it seems that one may arrive at $\exp(ipx)$ using these arguments.

If $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ represents $P(x)$ for a free particle, then $W(x) W(x)$ for the bound problem where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $W(x)$ is real (time reversal symmetry) should be by consistency $P(x)$ or spatial density for the bound system.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that classical mechanics, classical statistical mechanics and quantum bound systems even though at first appearing to be completely different may all represent constant energy together with time reversal symmetry which leads to a lack of information and

equilibrium. In other words equilibrium is represented by fundamental ideas which may apply to various different physical theories.

We note how time reversal symmetry appears for a classical particle $.5mv^2 + V(x) = E$, for $\exp(-(.5mv^2+V(x))/T)$ in classical statistical mechanics and for $\exp(-ipx)+\exp(ipx)$ in a bound quantum state such that $\cos(px)=\cos(-px)$. We note that constant energy is not enough for an equilibrium type situation. A classical particle moving on a surface with friction has conservation of overall energy, but the constraint of friction is not time reversal invariant. Playing a movie backwards is not the same as having the particle reverse directions. With friction it loses energy to heat moving in either direction.

We note that the idea of time reversal symmetry seems to be key for a quantum bound state. If one considers a classical action $-Et+px$ and tries to write a kind of probability based on $f(px)$ with x and t independent, then time reversal symmetry needs to appear for both an OR or AND situation. The OR situation applies to a physical interaction system with $V(x)$, thus $f(px) + f(-px) = \text{even function in } p$, but a free particle has uniform center-of-mass type motion so an AND situation should describe $P(x)$ classical = constant we suggest. Thus $f(px) f(-px) = \text{constant}$. This suggests a constant to the power of px while $f(px)+f(-px)$ suggests $\exp(ipx)$. Thus we argue that time reversal symmetry needed to establish an equilibrium type scenario might go further in quantum mechanics and actually define the form $\exp(ipx)$ and $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Reversal and Wavefunction(x,t)* Wavefunction(x,t)? (preprint, zenodo, 2022)